

DESTRUCTION OF RESISTANT OIL-WATER EMULSIONS USING BINARY SURFACTANT COMPOSITIONS

Savriyev Muhridin Sadriddinovich

Student, Bukhara engineering-technological institute, RUz, Bukhara

Email: savriyevmuhridin@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6055396>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th December 2021

Accepted: 25th January 2022

Online: 05th February 2022

KEY WORDS

crude oil, water content, quality, standard, field, preparation, commercial oil.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the composition of the oils produced in the local fields of Uzbekistan was studied and the quality indicators were compared with the requirements of the O'zDsT 3032:2015 standard. Based on the studied data, it is possible to evaluate commercial oil by its brands.

Introduction. When extracting a mixture of oil with formation water, an emulsion is formed, which should be considered as a mechanical mixture of two insoluble liquids, one of which is distributed in the volume of the other in the form of drops of various sizes [1].

Long-term practice shows that the destruction of each type of stable oil-water emulsion requires an individual approach to the selection of an effective demulsifier or their compositions with the determination of the optimal conditions for their use. Therefore, the solution to such a complex problem is achieved by using an integrated approach, which includes a number of physicochemical, technological and other types of research.

Research methods. Demulsifiers i.e. surfactants (surfactants) have the ability to lower the surface tension in the interfacial layer, because they selectively dissolve in one of the phases - a dispersion medium, concentrate at the interface and form there an adsorption layer in the form of a film. A

decrease in surface tension in this case contributes to an increase in the dispersion of the dispersed phase [2].

Resins, asphaltenes, asphaltogenic acids and their anhydrides, naphthenic acid salts, as well as various organic impurities accompanying oil, i.e. polar substances can usually serve as emulsifiers. Paraffins and ceresins also take part in the formation of stable oil-water emulsions [3].

In practice, hydrophobic emulsions are more often formed, in which resins, asphaltene substances, organic acid salts, etc. act as emulsifiers. Especially the presence of salts of naphthenic acids and asphalt-resinous substances leads to the formation of emulsions, characterized by high stability [3,4].

Moreover, the methods and techniques for increasing oil recovery, used today in practice to increase oil production, by injecting surfactant solutions, carbon dioxide, polymer solutions, micellar systems into the productive horizons, cause

changes in the composition and properties of stabilizers of the formed emulsions [5, 9].

The oil emulsion is stabilized by adsorption films, which are the physical barrier of contact between dispersed water droplets. These films are composed of natural oil emulsifiers of complex composition, which act in combination with inactive components. The main components of the boundary film are: porphyrin complexes, asphaltenes, resins, ions, mineral particles (clay, silt, sand, salts), paraffin microcrystals. According to [6], the thickness of these films (the so-called black films) in equilibrium is 300 Å.

As you can see, a wide variety of natural emulsifiers in the composition of oils, structuredness and a sufficiently high mechanical strength of the protective layers formed by them make it difficult to create universal demulsifiers for the destruction of emulsions. The necessary set of properties for the destruction of complex water-oil emulsions can provide a synergistic composition of demulsifiers based on surfactants of various chemical structures, i.e. substances with a high surface activity, an index of dispersing ability, the corresponding geometry of molecules, the ability to wet well a hydrophobic surface (inversion action), and good peptizing (deflocculating) properties. The combined action of these factors leads to an adsorption-displacing effect, which contributes to the complete destruction of stable oil-water emulsions [3-5].

Oil-soluble demulsifiers contain hydrophobic groups in combination with hydrophilic ones, and therefore they are always distributed between the hydrocarbon and aqueous phases in a ratio due to the properties of the demulsifier and the emulsion phases.

A water-soluble demulsifier, the distribution ratio of which is shifted towards the aqueous phase, is, for example, a block copolymer of propylene and ethylene oxides with a two-functional starting substance (Proxanol) [5].

In the US, a patent is protected [7], according to which a demulsifying composition has been developed to prevent the formation or separation of emulsions in aqueous solutions, which contains: (a) 1 salts of arylalkylsulfonic acid, effective for demulsifying the emulsion; (b) a first nonionic surfactant type stabilizing agent having the formula:

where R⁶- is C₈₋₁₆, R⁷-H alkyl C₁₋₆; x=2-20; (c) a second stabilizing agent consisting of mutually soluble solvents such as water-soluble glycol ethers, water-soluble amides, ketones and alcohols such as methanol, ethanol, propanol-1, propanol-2, wherein the mutual solvents solubilize components A and B.

In the Russian patent [8], it is proposed to use a hydrocarbon solvent (except for methyl ethyl ketontoluene) as a demulsifier, and carbamide or thiocarbamide or their mixture in dry form or in the form of an aqueous solution with a concentration of 0.01 to 6 %.

Research results. Taking into account this approach promising, we have created a number of binary surfactant compositions for demulsifying stable oil-water emulsions. The composition of the developed compositions included synthesized surfactants from fatty acids of cotton soap stock and natural nonionic ones.

Table 1 shows the main physicochemical characteristics of the selected surfactant compositions from the above components.

Table 1.

Basic physicochemical characteristics of selected surfactant compositions for demulsifying stable oil-water emulsions.

Name of the composition surfactants	Viscosity, sSt	pH	Surface tension, dyn / cm	Foaming capacity, at 25 °C, cm ³	Wetting ability
KD-1	0,73	7,7 ÷	55 ÷	250 ÷	16" ÷
		7,9	59	300	18"
KD-2	0,82	6,0 ÷	36 ÷	240 ÷	15" ÷
		7,3	38	270	17"
KD-3	0,94	7,1 ÷	25 ÷	350 ÷	12" ÷
		7,4	27	370	14"
KD-4	0,66	6,3 ÷	37 ÷	220 ÷	17" ÷
		6,9	39	260	20"

The discussion of the results. Table 1 shows that the obtained compositions of demulsifiers KD-1, KD-2, KD-3 and KD-4 differ significantly in their colloidal-chemical characteristics, despite the identity of the feedstock. Moreover, of the synthesized KD-1 has more preferable indicators than

Table 2 shows the results of demulsification of persistent oil-water emulsions of the Jarkurgan fields.

From table. 2. it can be seen that the developed compositions of demulsifiers KD-1, KD-2, KD-3 and KD-4 are effective surfactants and may well compete with the well-known KD (Russia). Moreover, in some cases, KD-1-KD-4 have better characteristics than the latter.

Output. Thus, the developed binary compositions of demulsifiers from local raw materials can completely replace the well-known surfactant compositions purchased from abroad at an expensive price.

Table 2.

Change in the settling time and the degree of dehydration of oil-water emulsions of the Dzharkurgan fields depending on the type of demulsifier compositions (CD) and their consumption

The name of the demulsifier composition	Demulsifier consumption,%	Emulsion settling time, h	The degree of dehydration of the emulsion,%
KD-1	0,010	5,5	35,1
	0,015	5,0	40,4
	0,020	4,7	48,3
KD-2	0,010	5,4	35,2
	0,015	4,8	37,5

	0,020	4,6	41,7
KD-3	0,010	5,5	33,5
	0,015	4,9	38,3
	0,020	4,5	40,2
	0,010	5,3	38,4
KD-4	0,015	5,0	40,7
	0,020	4,6	46,5
	0,010	5,2	38,4
KD (Russian) (Control)	0,015	5,0	40,7
	0,020	4,8	47,5

This undoubtedly contributes to a significant reduction in the cost of

preparation and processing of stable oil-water emulsions.

References:

1. Gurevich I.L. Technology of oil and gas processing. - M.: Chemistry, 1978- - 208p.
2. Gromov V.P. Destruction of emulsions during oil production. - M.: Nedra, 1974- - 241 p.
3. Gromov V.P. Field preparation of oil. - M.: Nedra, 1977.-181 p.
4. Pokonova Yu. Oil and petroleum products. Handbook. - M.: Chemistry, 2005. -515 p.
5. Bagirov I.T. Modern installations of primary oil refining. - Baku: Ilim, 1998. - 125 p.
6. Levchenko D.M. et al. Emulsions of oil with water and methods of their destruction. - M.: Chemistry, 1967. - 56 p.
7. Patent 6914036 (USA). IPC From 09 To 7/00.
8. Patent 2244733 (Russia), IPC From 106 33/04.
9. Sattorov, M. O., Yamaletdinova, A. A., & Bakieva, S. K. (2020). Analysis of the effectiveness of demulsifiers used in the destruction of local oil-water emulsions. *Universum: Technical Sciences*, (4-2 (73)), 52-58.
10. Sattorov, M. O., Yamaletdinova, A. A., & Bakieva, S. K. (2020). APPLICATION OF BINARY SYSTEMS OF SURFACTANTS FOR THE DEHYDRATION OF LOCAL OILS. *Universum: Technical Sciences*, (11-4 (80)).

